

A reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification for broad coverage detection of Asian and African Zika virus lineages

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Figure S1. Map of RT-LAMP primers in alignment with the ZIKV NS2-NS3 gene junction consensus sequences. The nucleotide positions refer to the published complete genome of ZIKV MR766 (GenBank accession number: NC_012532).